

A Study on the Function of Advertising Tools on Tourism a Case Study of Qeshm Free Zone

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Abstract:

The present study is done with the purpose of the function of advertising tools on the tourism industry's prosperity in Qeshm Island. The use of tools and factors affecting advertising is one of the factors that can develop and improve the country's tourism industry. One of the main factors in tourism marketing is the attraction of tourists to the region by way of advertising. Today, advertising should be used as the most important tool in the tourism industry professionally. In ancient Iran, Qeshm Island can be considered as a place where tourism in its centrality can contribute to the growth and development of the province of Hormozgan and this province has a lot of potentials to attract tourists. Hence, tourism advertising is considered as one of the necessary things to formulate marketing strategies for the tourism purposes of the province. Considering different types of advertising and features of Iran's tourism destinations, this research is looking to identify and use of appropriate advertising methods to attract and increase the number of tourists on Qeshm Island. Therefore, the area of tourism development needs strategic and planning and functional interaction with its environment more than ever, and those areas can hope for their future in attracting resources and delivering products which can take advantage of these emerging environmental opportunities and refrain from the threats posed by it. The facts indicate that the beautiful tourism Qeshm Island for greater compatibility with its peripheral environment must identify the factors affecting on the formulation of its development strategies and formulates the effective strategies. The tourism attraction in this region is no exception to this and it is faced with many environmental threats and opportunities. At present, the lack of strategic policy in this field causes the loss of environmental opportunities and aggravation of internal weaknesses. So, enjoying the approach of strategic planning makes the study area able to protect itself from other rivals and embarking upon basic missions in providing tourism products. The present research is a qualitative review of advertising tools in tourism in Qeshm Island.

Keywords: Tourism, Advertising tools, Industry, Free zone, marketing

1. INTRODUCTION

The prominent development of tourism industry in recent decades has made this industry as one of the most important economic-social activities of many countries in the world in such a way that it can be considered as a comprehensive system to facilitate and consolidate cultural, economic and social affairs. Also, the tourism sector could play an important role in the economy of societies and the exact identification of the market is the key to its development. On the one hand, although tourism is an international definition, but many individuals and organizations are active in the local or national market in this sector, and as a result, domestic tourism has a special place in the national economic cycle [3]. Tourism as one of the fastest economic sectors is growing. The leading countries in this dimension of the economic activities contribute the major share of their revenues from the arrival of the tourists annually. In fact, not only tourism is the world largest industry but it is rising day by day; in such a way that the World Tourism Organization predicts that number of tourists will reach to 1.5 billion people by 2020 [6].

In the tourism industry, advertising should be designed to describe the region so that people be attracted. This can be done with mass media such as newspapers, magazines, post, television, radio and more. The use of these tools indicates that advertisements are made by a specific medium. Sotoun deems advertising as one of the most effective ways to expose the demand. He says with regards to the framework provided by Kotler (1937), there are eight possible situations for demand, in all of which advertising plays an important role. According to him, the following model is obtained:

Advertising —————> Demand and, ultimately, industry development.

In this study, which has been presented in several studies seeks to identify the appropriate tools for the development of industry Tourism in Qeshm, therefore, in this research, seeks to identify a tool that influences on the Qeshm tourism industry.

Tourism industry, as the world's largest service industry, is now one of the key sources of economic prosperity (Job creation, foreign exchange earnings, poverty

alleviation, etc.), and the increase in social exchange and engagement. Thus, regions with tourism capacities should choose the right strategies to benefit from the economic and socio-cultural advantages of the aforementioned industry. Qeshm Island with an approximate area of 1491 square kilometers is located in the north of the strategic Strait of Hormoz, and with the three islands of Hormoz, Hengam and Larak constitutes Qeshm city in Hormozgan province. To formulate a tourism strategy in Qeshm Island, a comprehensive framework of formulating strategy has been used. In the start-up phase, the statement of the tourism mission of this region was determined.

2. Tourism

Tourism is one of the most important growing industries and the development of the tourism industry requires comprehensive and suitable plans to be able to attract international tourists. Today one of the most important functions of cities is providing new tourism services. Because the formation of the post-modern age is associated with its main proposition, that is, globalization, processing information and tourism, and has created a new era in the social and cultural interactions of humans specially in the form of urban constructions [1]. Tourism in its current sense dates back to the industrial revolution that its growing trend from the beginning to the present, in the twenty-first century, along with the information revolution has formed many topics around itself. In all the definitions given in the field of tourism, tourism includes all processes, such as travel planning, travel to the desired location; staying there (purchase and interacting with the host community), the return and remembrance of travel memories after return [2].

Tourism means traveling from a source to a destination for travel or trade, and its concept includes the processes of cultural, economic and social exchange. These factors, in total, create a network that the term travel or tourism is used for it. In addition, some experts have investigated tourism in the form of a source-destination network, for example, Pirce, referring to the multiple source-destination pattern of Tort in tourism definition has said: "Tourism is multifaceted, and since in its different stages from the sources to the destination, various services is requested and offered, it is geographically complex. Furthermore, there is probably a large number of source or destination in each country or region, that often they have both features of movement and acceptance [4]. Today, the ancient and historical monuments of cultural attractions are important factors in attracting tourism, because the ancient and old monuments of any society represent the specific culture of the same country and have features and values worthy of the same country and the land. These monuments have great spiritual values for

that nation and an attraction for others and thus cause the attraction of others to visit and discover those attractions and monuments. Discussion on various aspects of Iran traveling and tourism represents the difficulties and bottlenecks of the tourism industry in Iran, and the most important of which is the weakness of the advertising industry in attracting tourists to Iran. Despite Iran's capabilities in the field of tourism, unfortunately it has not so far been able to make a worthy position in this industry. Iran is among the top 10 countries in the world in terms of tourist attractions and is one of the world first five countries in terms of tourism diversity [8].

Many experts and professionals in the field of tourism have mentioned the effects and consequences of tourism development as follows [5]:

- Ensure the maintenance and development of physical infrastructure and public welfare services;
- Protection and preservation of historical monuments and buildings;
- Development of equipment and infrastructure services;
- Creation of new employment opportunities, bringing exchange and promotion of residents' living standards for tourism purposes;
- Preservation and dissemination of traditional arts and ancient customs;
- Revival of cultural identity and feeling national pride;
- Increase in cultural exchanges.

Hormozgan province in the south of the country due to the islands, historical sites, numerous beaches and natural phenomena has been able to attract part of the domestic and foreign tourism attentions. Qeshm as the largest Iranian island in the Middle East, with its diverse attractions, is the destination of domestic and foreign tourists. Free Zone since its establishment in the field of tourism and its development in Qeshm Island have begun activities and programs [10]. Due to historical antiquity, rich resources of attracting tourist and potential and actual capacities on Qeshm Island level and also due to the establishment of Nature Park in this area as the first Nature Park in the Middle East, examining the policies and strategies of tourism development considering the role of Qeshm Free Zone is of great importance. Formulation of practical strategies in this region can have an important role in attracting domestic and foreign tourists in this island and make sustainable development possible [11].

Managing Director of Qeshm Free Zone in 2010 introduces the most important actions that have been done in this island to introduce the tourism potentials as follows. [12]

Playing the Tourism Tone in Schools for one week, the presence of the society of Qeshm Hotel owners in the Specialty Show of Hotel Management in Mashhad with the goal of introducing accommodation facilities and

capacities in the region's hotels, a media tour for Tourism journalists aiming at introducing Qeshm as the Island of Seven Wonders of the Persian Gulf, special ceremony of tourism in Qeshm and launching Heaven Peacock rule of Qeshm for holding Sea Tourism Tours.

Therefore, taking into account that the measures taken in this field alone cannot solve the problem of tourism industry in this region, for this reason one of the most important strategies that can help the development of this industry in the region is using marketing and communication tools to identify the attractions of the island to domestic and foreign tourists [13]. Qeshm Free Zone Organization stated that Qeshm International Geopark has now gained a degree that can have sustainable income. It is expected that considering Qeshm International Geopark will provide for the growing international tourism development and consequently economic development and employment of a huge part of Islanders, along with proper care of the cultural heritage based on UNESCO's international standards. [19] With the global registration of this significant and incredible monument, we hope to be the witness of the increase in the number of tourists from different parts of the world at this point in Hormozgan province.

3. Advertising in the Tourism Industry

The tourism industry is a mixture of various activities that takes place as a chain to serve tourists, so tourism includes all the phenomena and the relations resulting from the interaction of tourists, suppliers and sellers of tourism products, governments and communities host in the process of attracting and receiving tourists. [9] Advertising refers to a set of public affairs that an organization or administration uses for a particular direction and purpose. [16] An operational definition of advertising variable includes: books and articles about Iran's tourism attractions, holding regular congresses and festivals to introduce the tourism attractions in Iran, attending tourism exhibitions inside and outside the country, using public media and covering the tourist attractions of Iran, utilizing global communication equipment such as satellite, internet, specialized-tourism magazines about tourism attractions of Iran, establishment of travel agencies abroad, inviting tourism writers and journalists to introduce more attractions of Iran and catalogs and photographs of Iranian tourism attractions. Advertising can be considered as an organized effort to monitor beliefs, theories, or acts of others, with the help of (signs, words, references, posters, memorabilia, music, clothing and labels) that have to be fully coordinated to create the maximum output [17]. But, what is commercial advertising? Dennis and DeFleur consider advertising to be a controlled form of communication that tries to persuade the target audience

to use or buy that product or service through the use of strategies and attractions. In this definition, persuasion is the key concept of the definition of advertising [35]. We consider advertising as a cultural code of society that interacts with other codes in society, in fact advertising is a system of signs in which the goods are the mail and the most important sign. People buy goods not just for what they are able to do, but for what they mean [36]. It can be clearly said that marketing and promotion is essential in the successful development of tourism, although it is easy to look at. Morgan (2002) states that traditional tourism marketing focuses on tourist objectives than more different and more recent methods. In addition, the marketing of tourism industry products is increasingly complex, the interconnected concept is not only to bring an image of a place, but also an attempt to bring the experience of a stage of life from customer to customer [15]. One of the most important, most effective and efficient ways to create a positive image and desirable mentality in the minds of potential tourists from tourism destinations and tourism products and, consequently, appropriate development of tourism is taking advantage of suitable and effective strategies and methods in the field of tourism marketing. [37]

Advertising changes the knowledge, attitude and behavior of the audiences. Awareness, encouragement and persuasion, recall, consolidation of relationships and acceleration and promotion of exchanges are among the various tasks of advertising and the evaluation of the effects of advertising on each of these cases is a necessity for organizations that consider advertising essential for survival and growth and development. [40].

4. Advertising tools in the tourism industry

Among the factors that can develop and improve the tourism industry is the use of effective tools and parameters of marketing and advertising, the most important factor of accelerating, the use of information and communication technology in the tourism distribution and marketing systems. Today, the role and influence of information and communication technology on the tourism industry is not hidden. Using the internet and the emergence of e-tourism, information and communication technology has become one of the basic elements of tourism and has increased the efficiency of this industry. The tourism system consists of five basic places of origin, the route of travel, the destination of the tourism industry and the external environment [7]. Advertising is carried out through a variety of media including newspapers, magazines, radio, television, etc. [18] The factor of the transmission of promotional messages also to impact on the behavior of various types of media includes newspapers, television, radio, and modern media such as the internet and billboards. Facilities that make

communication equipment available for advertising have caused that they have access to many people at the same time so that nowadays, people are not safe from advertising anywhere and are always exposed to bombardment of commercial advertising. Industry owners have learned that their ability to communicate effectively with the audiences is a very important factor in individual and organizational successes, and then they deal with advertising in creating an ideal image of products and services in the audience's mind with a more serious approach. Given the high cost of advertising, properly consuming advertising credits is of particular importance [49].

One of the most important steps in any advertising program is the evaluation of the effects of advertising. By examining the effects of advertising and its relationship with the organization's goals changes can be created in advertising budgets, the form and content of messages, and the type of media and communication channels and even the time and conditions for the implementation of advertising to make advertising more effective and effective than the past. The effects of advertising are very diverse and different, and therefore the isolation of each of them and even the effects of advertising in a period of time requires scientific and appropriate methods and techniques [40].

4.1. Modern tools in advertising

As with other service areas, the tourism industry is witnessing increased competition and the presence of new competitors. Along with this growth, the internet has become one of the most important sources of the information of futuristic tourists [19]. As defined by Hawkins (1994), internet advertising is defined as advertising that is sent for users of electronic services. This phenomenon was previously called electronic advertising [45]. Advertising content is a success factor in online advertising. If content is consistent with customer's attitudes, beliefs and values, the impact of advertising increases. The content of the internet advertising includes variables such as the overall appearance of the banner, background color, images, sound effects, textual content, creativity, rotation, interaction, size, position, and dynamic techniques. The attractive designing of content of the advertisement generates a positive perception of the brand and the goods, and it is likely to lead to the recall of the advertising content [38]. Today, the internet is used as a tool for marketing and major communications in the tourism industry. Therefore, it is not surprising that there exist discussions about the structural relationship between tourism and internet-based advertising. Using the structural equation model, the perception is that the connection and attention of consumer both have a direct

relationship with consumers' attitudes in advertising, they only indirectly affect respondent. The level of importance attributed to the internet advertising content has two different responses, which determined that the degree of consumer interference with the product is significantly different in determining success in internet advertising [20]. The internet is a good online guide to tourism. The internet tourism in addition to provide users with benefits such as informing tourism capacities, it also provides good executive facilities such as hotels online reservation, accommodation centers and ticket booking for airplanes and trains. In this way, it is possible for customers to take action in purchasing their ticket by eliminating intermediaries directly [42].

4-1-1 Internet advertising tools

Banner: A banner is a small graphic image and usually rectangular shaped that has different sizes and connects to another internet site. [21] A banner can have features such as the existence of links to send emails, using JavaScript to change color or image, being open and searchable menu. If the banner has these interactive features, it has a significant impact on the audience [43].

Sub-Sites: Sub-sites are small windows (smaller than normal size of browser window) that suddenly appear on the screen while surfing on the internet and contain promotional posts and images. These kinds of internet advertising are also known as jumper windows. Sub-sites can be divided into the following groups:

1) *Interstitials:* are windows separate from the main window of the browser that when the user enters a particular web site, or when it stops at that database appear on the display screen, and they usually remain on the page until the user close them.

2) *Superstitials:* These windows usually appear at the uploading interval of an internet database, and are spontaneously closed. In both types of sub-sites, advanced media technologies and techniques (richness media) may be used, or contain only text. Since, these kinds of internet advertising appear unpredictably without user's permission, and they may lead to the disturbance of the individuals focus have been criticized. However, they are widely used by databases, and the user's click rates are usually high. Industry tourism is not also disadvantaged from such developments. Since information is a vital element for the tourism industry, the dissemination of technologies has a major impact on demand and supply trends in this industry. The tourism industry is one of the most important and connecting industries between e-management and customers.

Search Engines: Search engines are referred to as internet databases that users can use them to search the content on the internet. These engines, after the user enters its

subject in the special form that has been embedded for this task, collect a list of the internet databases that contains the intended user's topic. The mechanism of the action of search engines that are also known as portals is typically in the following two forms: some of these databases using certain software applications named "crawlers" or "spiders", automatically search the internet to find the intended user's topic. These applications usually browse the internet daily and update their database. Internet databases (such as Google) also operate on the same mechanism. These engines usually allow the owners of the above mentioned databases to add their database properties to their database.

E-mail: Use of e-mail has a longer history. Internet advertising through banners, websites, and search engines are techniques that are only applied in the web, but e-mail is a subset of internet technologies and has been used many years before the web. However, the use of e-mail for advertising in recent years and with the increase in the number of internet users has been considered as such. [46]

4.1.2 Podcasting and vodcasting (image files) on the Internet

Podcasting definition according to Oxford dictionary is, "a new communication system and a method for the dissemination of electronic content by voice, through which the user puts the digital recorded program on the internet [22]. Podcasting is different from making simple media files available to download from a webpage or streaming (playing music while downloading it). When we do not have the appropriate bandwidth, using podcast is appropriate. In an interpretation, podcasting can be considered a mixture of radio, blogging, and TI Video [23]. Also Webster's New Millennium English Dictionary has introduced podcasting as publishing and propagating web (based on music with software that automatically identifies new files) and has pointed out that it can be accessible with the right to subscribe and join [24].

Vodcasting: It seems that after blogs and podcasts, it's now vodcastings turn to make another evolution in the cyber world. Vodcasts, which are also called videocasts and video podcasts are visual podcasts or in a simpler word are visual video files that are propagated in a special conditions in the World Wide Web. Vodcasting is actually presenting a kind of video content on the web through the R .S.S feed. A vodcasting formula can be summarized as follows: Internet + video file + Xml file that R.S.S output is some kind of it. The word vodcasting is derived from the two words "cast" and "vod". There is no doubt that the word cast stands for broadcasting means propagation, but about the first component of the word i.e. "vod", various explanations are provided in different sources. "Vod" has been cited somewhere as the short

form of the term "Video on Demand", and has been said elsewhere the video podcast, at first it was briefly converted to vidcast and then due to homophony with the word podcast has been turned into vodcast. [47]

This phrase refers to audiovisual files used by internet users. YouTube is the most famous internet sites for distributing such concepts. The role of the podcasting and vodcasting in intercultural relationships can be followed in topics related to tourism, cultural development, education, entertainment and informing. [98].

4.2 Traditional Tools in Advertising

Once the radio and the television, as electronic communication tools compared with the print and inscription that had a lifetime for many centuries were considered as modern media. But today, with the arrival of new media and digital and electronic developments that has taken place in this field, these media are among the traditional media. New communicational devices with a wide range of services have led to the emergence of a new era in media history. According to Jean Baudyard and Mark Pastr, as a new kind of society, they are different with the past. In their opinion, we are now passing (the media era) and witnessing (the second era of the media) [41]. In this research, traditional media refers to printed media (books and press), radio, television, and news agencies that lead the audiences through a linear narrative. [39].

Radio: Before the Second World War, and even the next years, radio was the only means that showed off among people. Almost all the walled families of the West, in the meantime, were listening to their favorite programs with different music. Today, despite the spread of television, radio continues to be used all over the world. *Magazine:* The magazine publishing industry in the world has undergone tremendous changes since its inception; these changes have been infiltrated in all dimensions of the industry. At the same time that the history of a magazine has remained constant and unchanged, but, the industry that supports the magazine and gives it life is always fluid and current. The growth of advertising in the magazines, their content diversity and other improvements are indicative of this changing environment. The magazine as an effective communicational medium is very important for advertising.

Television: Due to the unique feature that has in sending visual messages to the farthest points, the TV is one of the most sophisticated mass media, this complex and efficient media, in addition to broadcasting artistic programs (Such as movies, television serials, etc.) are responsible for the promotion of business, economic and cultural institutions [46].

In Iran's today tourism, according to the powerful media theory, media must pass through organizational

boundaries and with the professionalism and expertise of managers and staff make tourism organizations aware of the benefits of the presence of the tourist in the community and learn methods of dealing with them. The media at all stages from the start of the journey and after that have been with tourist and the host community also under the influence of the media is serving tourists ideally. Media in the communication and information era are considered as one of the most important means of reaching goals. Today communication plays an essential role in forming people's life and demands. Design, compilation and implementation of coherent programs bring forth public notification by the media, participation of the public and the increase in their perception of tourism. Tourism and the scientific and all-inclusive perception to it in Iran is one of the priorities that bring forth sustainable development. As a result, our country's natural and cultural attractions have the potential to be looked at with a more comprehensive and more inclusive approach and benefit from all the capabilities and facilities available in this direction. One of these opportunities is rules and regulations set in this regard that a part of it is large and another part emphasizes on the development of tourism through media obviously. In quantitative goals the document of tourism twenty-year vision of attracting twenty million tourists, in general it has been stated that access to it needs addressing executive strategies and developing plans and strategies that meet the above goal and in this relationship, media strategies should also be specified and determined. So providing such patterns and researches is expected from the country's scientific system and makes access to the goals more practical, while in terms of newness, it provides grounds for further, deeper and wider researches [50]. Often, the transmission of advertising messages is the responsibility of the media and the means of attracting public participation is the mass media that is like a mediating force among people. The media, as communicational channels, transfer the same messages simultaneously to heterogeneous audiences who have access to it [26]. Media is the most important and most effective means of transmitting information and knowledge in the realization of the communication process. In the Farsi dictionary "Amid" it is said: any means that informs people of the matter or media news against the word, such as radio and television and newspaper. Today, with the help of new technology and the growth of tools for transferring information and exchanging ideas and opinions through the press, radio and television, the structure of traditional media has been disturbed and the communication world has entered a new stage in its life. Media (radio, television, the press, cinema, etc.) are tremendous tools that embody the technological advancement of humans and have caused

the throw of communities to the future. These issues has taken a dramatic part in the emergence of new habits, the development of new global cultures, change in the behavior and mood of humans and ways of life, and finally outgrow of the Earth and the neighborhood of distant nations. As some have regarded the present age "the age of communication" [51]. Qeshm Free Zone stated that after the establishment of indigenous residences in the villages of Qeshm and the introduction of historical and natural attractions of this island in the media, the desire of travelers from markets and business centers to the wilderness and visiting beauties of visitation Qeshm has been increased. The statistics of the number of traffic in rural quays such as Shibderaz, Kandalo, Laft and Soheili in this New Year is higher than the statistics of traffic in the whole last year. Expressing the increase in tourists' durability in Qeshm Island, the rate of tourist's maintenance has reached 4.8 days this year, while it was only 1.8 days last year. This New Year, 17% of tourists from Tehran province, 14% of Razavi Khorasan, 13% of Isfahan, 11% of Fars, six percent of Kerman, five percent of Hormozgan and the rest of the other provinces of the country traveled to Qeshm. Cultural heritage, handicrafts and tourism Organization of Qeshm's Free Zone said, according to surveys conducted over 80% of Norouz's guests were fully satisfied with the behavior of the local community [27].

5. Tourism advertising in Qeshm Island

Qeshm Tourism Organization and Qeshm Free Zone Organization have done many efforts to attract tourists to Qeshm Island. In order to promote the development of the tourism industry, they have been engaged in promotional activities to introduce the island to people inside and outside the country that are briefly mentioned below.

5.1. Tourism Website of Qeshm Free Zone Organization

One of the important activities of Qeshm Tourism Organization is the creation of a website. On this website, visitors are provided with complete information of Qeshm Island, tourism attractions, traffic information and complete map of Qeshm with image. This website has been presented in English and Persian.

5.2. Releasing advertising teaser of Qeshm Island at 17 airports in the country

In Qeshm Free Zone, the 20 second teaser of Qeshm tourism capacities was broadcasted from April ninth, 2017 every day for three thousand seconds from any airport television for one month. Qeshm advertising teaser was broadcasted during this time at Imam Khomeini and Mehrabad Tehran, Isfahan, Ahvaz, Abadan, Bandar Abbas, Bushehr, Birjand, Tabriz, Rasht, Zahedan, Sari, Shiraz, Kerman, Kermanshah, Mashhad

and Yazd airports. The executive staff of Qeshm travel agency continued: these 17 airports are located in provinces that have the most frequent tourism intercommunication with Qeshm Island and broadcasting these teasers through 543 airport televisions will play an important role in the increase in attracting tourists to Qeshm Island. The content of this clip is the introduction of recreational and tourism capacities of Qeshm Island, including natural attractions, marine recreations like jet skis, diving, competitions such as camel riding, cross motor, safari piste, flying with paraglider, shopping centers and other recreational facilities in Qeshm Island. In addition to the airport televisions, eight advertising boards have been given to the Qeshm Free Zone Organization at the Transit Hall of Terminal No. 2 of the Mehrabad Airport. Executive staff of Qeshm Travel Services stated that on these boards the slogan: "Qeshm is something else this year", tourism attractions, required information on trip to the Island, and communicational ways with the Qeshm Free Zone Organization have been stamped. Qeshm Island with an area of 1,500 square kilometers and an around 120,000 population with important capacities of the scope of tourism such as the longest saline cave in the world, the Mangrove forests, Naz islands, Stars Valley, Chahkuh Valley, Khaorbas Caves, spawning site of eagle muzzle turtles, Portuguese Castle, Tala wells, Exclusive windsurfers, mountains, beautiful beaches, Geopark museum, Sculptures Valley, Qeshm Roof, Guest Tents in Villages, beautiful palm trees, delicious foods and most importantly the hospitality of the noble people of the island are considered as one of the most important tourism points in Iran, which hosts millions of travelers and tourists from different parts of Iran and the world throughout the year [28].

5.3. Beginning the activity of Qeshm Ava radio (a new and comprehensive media in the island)

Public Relations of Qeshm Free Zone Organization has launched this radio as an internet radio (podcast) with the aim of the more and better informing people and creating a spirit of hope and life in the community in the form of a new and inclusive media for transparency of government activities, responsibility of authorities to the people and empathy of the island's inhabitants with the authorities. Introducing the geosites of the only Middle East Geoparks in Qeshm, which will be soon confirmed by the UNESCO experts among the world geoparks is also of other important issues that will be talked about on Qeshm's Ava radio [29].

5-4. Qeshm in National Media (the presence in television news programs)

The increase of travel to Qeshm Island in 2016 and 2017 New Year Qeshm Free Zone stated that from Mars 15, 2016 to the end of the first day of April 2017, 170.96

individuals through the land, air and sea entered Qeshm Island, reflecting a 29% increase in passengers' arrival over the same period of the last year with 132,133 individuals. He continued: during this time, 31,512 vehicles entered Laft port in Qeshm Island through Pol pier in Bandar-e-Kermir using vessels special for shipping (landing crafts), which in comparison with the same period of last year and 233,46 vehicles grew by 35%. According to the chairman of the committee notification and advertisement of Executive Staff of Qeshm's travel agency, during the mentioned period 37.651 tourists visited Qeshm's tourism sites that have a growth of 19% compared to the same period with 31,719 tourists [30].

Public Relations of Qeshm Free Zone Organization said: in Nowruz holiday in 2017, more than 118.000 vehicles entered Laft pier of Qashem Island through Pol port in Hormozgan province, which this amount has six percentage increases than the last year. According to him, over the same period, more than 31.000 passengers traveled to the island from Qeshm International Airport that had a dramatic growth of 54 percent over the same period last year. The deputy of Executive Staff of Qeshm Travel Services stated: On the thirteenth day of spring, 2017, more than eight thousand people traveled to the island that seven thousand people entered the island from the quays and a thousand people from the airport. Qeshm Island with an area of 1.500 km² is located in southern Iran and the Strait of Hormoz and each year hosts millions of domestic and foreign tourists. This New Year, despite the unprecedented rainfall on the island hundreds of thousands of compatriots chose this beautiful island as a travel destination [31].

6. Features of the area under study

The area under study is Qeshm Island. Qeshm Island is the largest island of the Strait of Hormoz and the Persian Gulf and the Persian Gulf and the most populous island of Iran. Once, the island has been well-off and prosperous. The city of Qeshm is at the eastern part of Island. Laft port is located in the middle, and Basaido port in the western part of the island, it has 75 villages. The length of the Qeshm Island is about 115 km, while the width of the island is different insofar as the width of the island in the city of Qeshm is about 5 km and in the part of Basaido, about 11 Km and in Laft port around 31 Km. The total area of the island is 1093 square kilometers and the length of Qeshm Island coasts is equal to 275 km. The island had various names, before Islam it has been called Berakht. Later on it was named Laft (which is now one of its northern ports) and then it was called Qeshm which was one of its ports, that today is famous with the same name [32]. Persian Gulf Coasts and Oman Sea are of great importance in the field of tourist activities;

meanwhile, Qeshm Island with natural landscapes and cultural monuments has a special tourism value. This island has a seven-month summer season and a five-month spring season. Although in the summer period with attention to the island's function in the Free Zone particularly in terms of business attracts tourists, but in the spring season, due to the favorable climate conditions and the beautiful landscape of the island, the presence of tourists is more intense. Therefore, the island can attract thousands of tourists due to special geographical location and having capacities and capabilities of natural and cultural environment [33]. The beautiful and big island of Qeshm with many natural attractions is one of the main tourism hubs in Iran. Beautiful nature, heights and mountains, ancient monuments, beaches, mangroves, etc. can make this island the most wealthiest places in terms of attracting tourists. On the other hand, many attractions like Qeshm's Mangroves, the Stars Valley and intact nature [34] along with civilization and ancient cultural monuments and indigenous people have caused the island to become one of the country's tourism centers. [50]

7. CONCLUSIONS

In the end, it can be said that for advertising activities in the tourism industry in today's world, advertising must be looked at with this belief and faith that advertising is not expensive, but it is a kind of fundamental and principled investment for advancement of organizational and national goals and, in case of proper and correct implementation can have valuable achievements. It should be noted that the development of the tourism industry and advertising in a specific process are in close contact with each other. Because the tourism industry in the development process is part of the economic production structure that can play an important and fundamental role in countries in the development of production and income and job creation. To develop in the travel and tourism industry, which can bring many economic, social, political and cultural achievements for its pioneers, and what we need in today's world is referred to as advertising, today's ads can give people new ideas, beliefs and mindsets. According to research in the area under study, a situation that Qeshm Island has, as well as different potentials whether in terms of both tourism and business and tourist attraction in all seasons or the presence of historical, commercial, recreational attractions from Qajar period, is the main advantage of this region for the development of tourism. In today's world, promotional and marketing efforts is by far more important than production and sale, so if a country has the potential capabilities and facilities of tourism, but does not put advertising method and the introduction of these attractions and potentials in its macro program, certainly it will not be successful in the growth and the

development of its tourism industry. Tourism planners should try to make proper tangible products and give them a good memory. This good experience will act as a positive advertising and creating an appropriate image in the minds of tourists. Tourism organization and Qeshm Free Zone using the advertisements in the national media could introduce Qeshm's tourism attractions with a brand called Seven Wonders of the Persian Gulf, and also with the globalization of Qeshm Geopark it plays an effective role in attracting foreign and domestic tourist. And with the advertising in the national media can have the 2% growth in tourists in 2017 compared to 2016. In sum, it can be said that if tourism of Qeshm Island wants to be more developed, it requires fundamental planning in advertising.

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